

NDAC/LO/056

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SAMPLE RESULTS FROM A TEST RUN OF STEP 2/3

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Input data

Simulated input data as described in NDAC/LO/048, but restricted to the first 10000 stars and 730 sets (1.0 year). The 'Input Catalogue' errors are: 1 arcsec rms in position, 30 mas/yr in p.m.; a priori parallaxes = 0. Total number of observations = 131,521. (By accident, the observations were lost for one star, so the statistics below are actually for 9999 stars.)

Adjustment

Three astrometric parameters per star were adjusted (α , δ , Π) in ACCU23. In the other program, SOLV23, the set zero points and four global parameters (the first two sine and cosine terms of the basic angle harmonics) were adjusted. Due to the presence of the sine global parameter, the parallax zero point is undefined (cf. Fig. 4).

Iterations

Five iterations were made, by running alterately ACCU23 and SOLV23 (cf. the command file on p. 2). The adjusted astrometric parameters were compared, after each iteration, with true values from a special file. The rms adjustment of the set zero points were as follows:

in the 1st iteration:	rms Δc_j	= 60.7 mas
" " 2nd	"	5.16 mas
" " 3rd	"	0.0046 mas
" " 4th	"	0.0000086 mas
" " 5th	"	0.0000016 mas

The astrometric parameters did not change, in practice, after the 3rd iteration. Their evolution can be seen in Figs. 2 - 4.

Slit errors

The frequency of false positions due to slit errors was, in the first iteration 16.2 %, in the 2nd 0.26 %, and in the 3rd and following 0.16 %. Figs. 5 and 6 show the distributions of the DOF and $\Delta\chi^2$ for the true and false positions in the 1st iteration.

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nice compare >out0
nice accu23 <stf200
nice compare >out1
nice solv23 <stf200 >z200
nice accu23 <stf201
nice compare >out2
nice solv23 <stf201 >z201
nice accu23 <stf202
nice compare >out3
nice solv23 <stf202 >z202
nice accu23 <stf203
nice compare >out4
nice solv23 <stf203 >z203
nice accu23 <stf204
nice solv23 <stf204 >z204

```

UNIX command file for 4 Step 2/3 iterations

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STARTING FILE FOR STEP 2/3 PROGRAMS accu23, solv23

INPUT FIELD	COMMENTS
200	irun
.TRUE.	matrix = .TRUE. to compute full matrix
.TRUE., 5	zptvar = .TRUE. to calc every ith zpt var.
'status'	status file (filename)
'objcat'	object catalogue (filename)
'rgccat'	RGC catalogue (filename)
'glbcat'	global param. cat. (filename)
'neqfil'	normal equations (filename)
'obscoat'	observations (filename)
'asylum'	asylum (filename)
'logfil'	log (filename)
3	naspar = astrometric parameters/star
4, 1,2,3,4	nnglb, list of global parameters in ACCU23
0	nxglb, list of globals excluded in SOLV23
2000	nrgo = number of entries in rgcoat
730	nset = number of sets
1,730	set limits (first, last)
.70, 4.	rstep, rmax (for MESH)
100., 1.	max acceptable t1, scale (MESH chi2 test)
500.	min acceptable delta(chi2) for unambiguity

The starting file for the 1st iteration of accu23 and solv23

Fig. 1. Formal mean error of abscissa zero points (every 5th set).
These are calculated from the pseudoinverse of the normal equations matrix. The condition number of the normals was 360,000.

Fig. 2. Distribution of position errors $[(\Delta\alpha \cos \delta)^2 + (\Delta\delta)^2]^{\frac{1}{2}}$ after 1st iteration, illustrating the slit errors for 1621 out of the 9999 stars (top). The histogram below shows the 8378 stars without slit errors in an expanded scale.

Fig. 3. Distribution of position errors $[(\Delta\alpha \cos \delta)^2 + (\Delta\delta)^2]^{\frac{1}{2}}$:
 before adjustment (top), $\sigma = 992$ mas
 after 1st iteration (bottom), $\sigma = 32.5$ mas

Fig. 3 (continued). Distribution of position errors:
after 2nd iteration (top), $\sigma = 15.5$ mas
after 3rd iteration (bottom), $\sigma = 15.2$ mas

Fig. 4. Parallax error distribution: before adjustment (top)
after 1st iteration (bottom), $\sigma = 38$ mas

Fig. 4 (continued). Parallax error distribution:
after 2nd iteration (top), $\sigma = 6.45$ mas
after 3rd iteration (bottom), $\sigma = 5.37$ mas

Fig. 5. Distribution of $\text{DOF} = (\text{number of observations per star}) - 3$.

Top: all 9999 stars

Bottom: the shaded histogram is for the 1621 stars with slit errors after the 1st iteration

Fig. 6. Distribution of $\Delta\chi^2 =$ difference in χ^2 between the best fit and next best fit in MESH algorithm.

Top: for the 8378 stars without slit errors in 1st iteration

Bottom: for the 1621 stars with slit errors in 1st iteration